

VibroCalm Research Helmet - Brainwave Modulation Prototype

A research concept for a helmet designed to explore low-frequency vibration and brainwave modulation for relaxation and anesthetic-related studies.

This is a research-only idea, intended for scientific investigation and experimentation.

Note: No commercial or clinical instructions are included.

Researchers or professionals in anesthesiology and neuroscience interested in collaborating or learning more about the technical details are welcome to contact me directly.

Contact: Mary Gamal - marygamal18011981@gmail.com

Keywords: Brainwave modulation, Vibroacoustic therapy, Research prototype, Anesthesiology research, Neuroscience, Experimental device, Helmet, Non-invasive stimulation, Vibrotherapy